

Review of VLSI Architecture of Filterbank for Hearing Aids

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Abstract— Hearing aids have undergone significant advancements in recent years, driven by the need for high-performance signal processing systems that are energy-efficient, compact, and capable of real-time operation. Among the various components of hearing aid devices, the filterbank plays a critical role in analyzing and processing audio signals. The Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) architecture for filterbanks has emerged as a vital area of research, addressing challenges such as power consumption, latency, and computational efficiency. This review provides a comprehensive analysis of VLSI architectures for filterbanks specifically tailored for hearing aid applications. It highlights various filterbank designs, including Finite Impulse Response (FIR), Infinite Impulse Response (IIR), and Wavelet Transform-based approaches. Additionally, the paper discusses key parameters such as power optimization, silicon area utilization, and adaptability to dynamic audio environments.

Keywords—Filterbank, Subband, Channel, Delay, Complex, Hearing Aid .

I. Introduction

Hearing impairment is a pervasive health issue affecting millions of individuals worldwide. With the increasing prevalence of hearing loss due to aging populations, noise pollution, and genetic factors, the demand for advanced hearing aid technologies has grown exponentially. Modern hearing aids are no longer limited to basic sound amplification; instead, they incorporate sophisticated digital signal processing (DSP) systems to enhance auditory perception in complex environments. Among the essential components of these systems is the filterbank, which decomposes audio signals into distinct frequency bands for further analysis and processing.

The design and implementation of filterbanks pose significant challenges due to the stringent requirements of hearing aids. These devices must operate under ultra-low power conditions to ensure prolonged battery life while maintaining real-time performance and compact form factors. Additionally, hearing aids must adapt to diverse acoustic environments, including noisy backgrounds and rapidly changing soundscapes. To meet these demands, researchers have explored various VLSI architectures for filterbanks, leveraging advances in semiconductor technology and digital design methodologies.

Filterbanks in hearing aids are typically implemented using FIR or IIR filter structures, with each approach offering distinct advantages and trade-offs. FIR filterbanks are known for their stability and linear-phase characteristics, making them suitable for applications requiring high audio fidelity. On the other hand, IIR filterbanks provide computational efficiency and reduced hardware complexity,

albeit at the cost of potential phase distortion. Recent innovations have also introduced wavelet transform-based filterbanks, which offer multi-resolution analysis capabilities, enabling enhanced processing of non-stationary audio signals.

The evolution of VLSI architectures has played a pivotal role in addressing the constraints of hearing aid applications. Low-power design techniques, such as clock gating, voltage scaling, and dynamic power management, have been widely adopted to minimize energy consumption. Concurrently, architectural optimizations, including parallel processing and pipelining, have been employed to achieve real-time performance. Moreover, advancements in fabrication technologies, such as nanoscale CMOS, have enabled the development of highly compact and efficient filterbank circuits.

This review explores the current landscape of VLSI architectures for filterbanks in hearing aids, focusing on key design considerations and performance metrics. It examines various filterbank implementations, including their advantages, limitations, and suitability for specific hearing aid applications. Furthermore, the review delves into emerging trends, such as machine learning integration and bio-inspired design paradigms, which hold promise for revolutionizing hearing aid technology.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of filterbank fundamentals and their role in hearing aids. Section 3 discusses traditional VLSI architectures for filterbanks, highlighting their design methodologies and performance trade-offs. Section 4 examines recent advancements in low-power and high-

performance filterbank architectures, with an emphasis on their application in hearing aids. Section 5 identifies research gaps and future directions, offering insights into potential innovations. Finally, Section 6 concludes the review by summarizing key findings and their implications for next-generation hearing aid systems.

By synthesizing the vast body of research on VLSI-based filterbanks, this review aims to provide a valuable resource for researchers and practitioners working in the fields of biomedical signal processing, VLSI design, and hearing aid development. Through a detailed analysis of current technologies and emerging trends, the paper seeks to inspire novel solutions to the challenges posed by hearing aid applications, ultimately contributing to the enhancement of auditory experiences for individuals with hearing impairments.

II. Literature Survey

A. K. Samantaray et al., [1] presented a novel generalized approach to obtain rational (dyadic and integer) bi-orthogonal wavelet filter coefficients based on two conditions, namely maximally flatness and near-perfect reconstruction (PR) in half-band polynomial (HBP). An incremental-iterative approach is adopted to design the coefficients based on the proposed error equation in terms of the remainder polynomial (RP) of Lagrange HBP and the proposed HBP with maximum vanishing moments (VMs). In addition, VLSI architecture for the proposed wavelet filter banks (FBs) is designed and implemented on the Zedboard ZYNQ-7000 AP-SoC (Zynq FPGA from Xilinx) field-programmable gate array. It is found that the proposed rationalized wavelet FBs achieved significantly low digital hardware requirements with similar characteristics when compared to well-known rationalized existing bi-orthogonal wavelet FBs.

K. Kaustubh Bannintha et al.,[2] presents a system with reconfigurable warped VDF that uses a single prototype filter for generating all the necessary sub-bands. The proposed system automates the generation of the control signals for reconfiguring the filter and pipelines the processing of each sub-band to generate the requisite magnitude response. The proposed architecture is designed to achieve good audiogram matching with minimum matching error.

S. C. Lai, C. H. Liu et al.,[3] presents a novel algorithm design of 18-band quasi-class-2 ANSI S1.11 1/3 octave filter bank with the advantages of low group delay and low complexity. The proposed method utilizes a simple low-pass filter (LPF) and discrete cosine transform (DCT) modulation to generate a uniform 9-band filter bank first, and then transfer all element of z^{-1} into all-pass filter in order to

obtain the non-uniform filter bank to meet the standard. Quasi-class-2 ANSI S1.11 design, the proposed method totally has 63.4% reduction for multiplications per sample and 14-ms group delay, although we still have 15.2% increase for additions per sample.

A. Vijayakumar et al.,[4] shows that the design criteria of p th order analysis having q th order synthesis filters ($p \neq q$) with a flexibility to control the system delay has never been addressed concomitantly. In this paper, we propose a systematic design for a filterbank that can have arbitrary delay with a (p, q) order. Such filterbanks play an important role especially in applications where low delay-high quality signals are required, like a digital hearing aid.

Y. Wei et al.,[5]. the proposed filterbank can achieve a better matching to the audiogram and has smaller complexity compared with the fixed filterbank. The drawback of the proposed method is that the throughput delay is relatively long (>20 ms), which needs to be further reduced before it can be used in a real hearing-aid application.

A. Schasse, et al.,[6] present an efficient method to increase the frequency resolution for speech enhancement algorithms in hearing aids. Since the analysis-synthesis filter-bank applied in digital hearing aids needs to deliver a high stop band attenuation to enable large frequency dependent amplification gains and a low overall delay, speech enhancement often suffers from the resulting low frequency resolution. This leads to residual noise artifacts in the processed speech, since the noise between the harmonics can not be removed.

R. Dong et al.,[7] To help develop ultra-low power wireless hearing aid products, we investigate the integration of subband audio coding with hearing aid applications. Both the audio coding and the hearing aid application use subband processing, but their requirements for the filterbanks are totally different. A joint filterbank structure is proposed in this paper to satisfy these contradictive filterbank requirements. With this structure, the two filterbanks are combined into a single stereo filterbank operation, which can be efficiently implemented on a filterbank coprocessor. This structure substantially reduces the computation complexity, power consumption and memory usage.

R. Vicen-Bueno et al.,[8] presents the categories, the added stable gain (ASG) value over the limit gain of the digital hearing aids is obtained. The ASG value is achieved as a tradeoff between the segmented signal-to-noise ratio (objective parameter) and the speech quality (subjective parameter). The results show how the digital hearing aid working with a feedback reduction adaptive filter adapted

with the NFXLMS algorithm is able to achieve up to 18 dB of increase over the limit gain.

R. Vicen-Bueno, R. Gil-Pita et al.,[9] presents the description of a hearing aid simulation tool. This tool simulates the real behavior of digital DSP-based hearing aids with the aim of getting a very promising performance, which can be used for further design and research, and for a better fitting of the hearing impaired patient. Results using a multilevel multifrequency hearing aid with real data collected from 18 patients show how the multifrequency compression techniques adapt the normal perceptible sounds to the hearing impaired patient perceiving area.

B. Swanson et al.,[10] The Nucleus Freedom cochlear implant system enables a profoundly deaf person to hear. The system consists of a surgically implanted stimulator and a battery-powered external sound processor. The processor is based on a 0.18 μm CMOS ASIC containing four DSP cores. The signal processing includes a two-microphone adaptive beamformer, a 22-channel quadrature FFT filterbank, multi-band automatic gain control, a psycho-acoustic masking model and non-linear compression. The key design challenge was power consumption.

III. Hearing Aid Application & Challenges

For hearing aid use, the frequency splitting is performed for the purpose of modifying the spectral shape of the input signal. Hearing aid fitting typically requires a wide gain adjustment range. In a compression system, the input signal level, which can be measured as the overall level, channel level or a combination, controls these gains.

The spectral shape of the input signal is modified at this point by applying suitable gains to the frequency channel signals. This is followed by the corresponding inverse odd (even) FFT, interpolation, synthesis window weighting and the overlap-add procedure. This window (a low-pass filter which is the counterpart to the analysis window), minimizes the spectral imaging distortion created during the interpolation step.

Given the requirement for wide gain adjustment, the alias cancellation theory is invalid and critical sampling is insufficient. This problem necessitated the development of an oversampled filterbank. Although oversampling increases the data rate, it is the price that must be paid for gain adjustability without aliasing. In a compression system, gain changes are dynamic. This may cause anomalies in the overall frequency response if phase differences exist between adjacent bands.

To avoid these undesirable frequency response notches or peaks at the band edges (which frequently occur in analog

systems), it is necessary to constrain the filter channel impulse responses to be linear phase and of equal delay.

Thus, an ideal filterbank for a hearing aid application would:

- Allow precise fitting of prescriptive targets
- Have short delay
- Be computationally efficient
- Use a minimal amount of memory.

IV. Conclusion

This paper studies about the various researches on the digital filter bank for the hearing aid applications. Several tradeoffs have been made to make filterbank that can meet the requirements of a hearing aid application. The filterbank structure is M-band with uniform bands. This type of structure provides many advantages in a hearing aid context. To conserve memory, only a single analysis window is stored. To further reduce memory, the synthesis window is created by decimating the analysis window, subject to time and frequency domain constraints that can be satisfied by using an filter design method.

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